

Exploring the Entrepreneurial Intentions of Graduating Engineering Students: The Moderating Role of Internship Quality at Kenyatta University, Kenya

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Abstract: This study employs Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model to investigate the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions among final-year university engineering students, with a specific focus on the role of internship quality. Employing a positivist exploratory approach and a cross-sectional survey design, the study utilized non-probabilistic sampling of final-year undergraduates at Kenyatta University who had completed industrial internships. Data collection involved a Likert scale questionnaire distributed via email and WhatsApp, and data analysis utilized Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The study's outcomes, derived from the Structural Equation Model, reveal a positive influence of Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intentions, supporting hypothesis (H2). It emphasizes the inclination of engineering students towards self-employment, driven by a need for autonomy, positively affecting their Entrepreneurial Intentions (H4). However, the link between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intentions lacked statistical significance, negating hypothesis (H1), and the positive association between the Need for Achievement and Entrepreneurial Intention was not confirmed (H3). Internship Quality was identified as a positive moderator for the effects of Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention, affirming hypothesis (H5). Yet, the moderation of the influence of Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intention by Internship Quality was not deemed significant, leading to the rejection of hypothesis (H6). The study recommends expanding the engineering curriculum to include entrepreneurial skills, government support for youth entrepreneurship, and promotion of an entrepreneurial culture among engineering graduates by regulatory bodies. Collaboration between educational institutions, regulatory bodies, and entrepreneurial organizations is crucial, with a focus on preparing engineers for industry demands. The study advocates for providing entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to engineering students, government capital for aspiring entrepreneurs, and specialized training in innovative product and service development. Additionally, it suggests organizing trade fairs and seminars to enhance the recognition of entrepreneurs' contributions to the economy.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Engineering Graduates, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Developing Countries

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Introduction

In developing countries, a pressing concern is the reduction of unemployment (Ayalew, 2018), heightening the significance of entrepreneurship for development. Many nations have implemented policies recognizing entrepreneurship as a strategic factor for economic growth (Hue et al., 2022). Utilizing advanced technologies enhances macroeconomic efficiency, leading to increased employment opportunities and overall progress in national development goals (United Nations, 2008). Recognizing the positive impact of entrepreneurship on economic growth, promoting entrepreneurial intentions becomes a crucial focus, particularly within university and college education. Research indicates that students engaging in entrepreneurial activities during their college years are more likely to become future entrepreneurs (Astuty *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, there exists an inverse correlation between education levels and access to formal employment, with lower education levels associated with greater youth involvement in the informal sector (Stella, 2016). To address youth unemployment, universities and colleges must actively facilitate and encourage entrepreneurial interest among students (Ngugi and Gakure, 2012). The United Nations (2018) underscores the need for quality education, encompassing a comprehensive curriculum and various education opportunities to align with economic demands. In Kenya, engineering education plays a pivotal role in the country's economic agenda, but there is a mismatch between the skills provided by the education system and the dynamic engineering sector (Rutto, 2015). The global market's evolving dynamics necessitate a paradigm shift in engineering training, with a call for engineers to possess multidisciplinary skills, creativity, adaptability, and high ethical standards (Rutto, 2015; Jarrar and Anis, 2016).

Various inquiries have sought to investigate entrepreneurial intentions (EIs) among university students. For instance, Yi (2018) conducted a study involving graduating engineering students in China, aiming to scrutinize the positive correlation between internship quality and entrepreneurial intentions (EIs). Employing Shapero's Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) and employing structural equation modeling (SEM), the study illustrated a notable and direct/indirect influence of internship quality on students' EIs, mediated through entrepreneurial desirability and feasibility. This underscores the crucial role of internships in molding university students' EIs, highlighting the necessity for improved internship quality to foster students' entrepreneurial desirability and feasibility. On the other hand, Valencia-arias et al. (2020) investigated entrepreneurial intentions in Colombian engineering students using the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB). Their findings highlighted the influence of attitudes, perceived behavioural control, current behavioural control, and entrepreneurial behaviour on students' intentions to start a business, with current behavioural control identified as most influential. The study, employing statistical Somers' D analysis, emphasized the need for future research on the influence of social groups. In our study, we will use the Entrepreneurial Event Model to explore the moderation role of internship quality in the relationship between entrepreneurial feasibility, desirability, and intentions among engineering students. Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo (2018) focused on the entrepreneurial intentions of industrial and computing engineering students in Spain, identifying the need for independence as a key driver, positively influenced by entrepreneurship education. The study employed economic-psychological methods, including PCA, descriptive analysis, and linear regression, emphasizing the impact of entrepreneurial motivations and education on future engineers' intentions. Arango-botero et al. (2020) studied factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students in Colombia, finding positive impacts of attitude and entrepreneurial behaviour, while subjective norms had no influence on starting a new business. In Kenya, Ngugi and Gakure (2012) investigated the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions among postgraduate students, using Shapero's model and ANOVA, revealing the significant influence of the propensity to act and individual perception of venture feasibility. This study aims to contribute by examining Shapero's model in explaining entrepreneurial intentions among graduating engineering students at Kenyatta University, Kenya.

According to Ayalew (2018), studies on the entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates have focused mainly on developed countries hence less focus on developing countries. It calls therefore for more focus on the latter particularly

due to the current crisis and high unemployment rates in the developing countries. Biko (2020) adds that academic research on entrepreneurship has not been widespread in African countries which have factor-driven economies and have been noted not to provide conducive environment for entrepreneurial activities. Furthermore, low post-school entrepreneurship education, as compared to developed countries, is yet another factor undermining progress in entrepreneurship for developing countries. Moreover, few studies have analysed and identified the entrepreneurial intentions of university students in undergraduate programs with a technological focus, such as engineering; yet the group is perceived to represent a critical group in society which policies to promote technology-based entrepreneurship should target (Arango-botero *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the labour market is increasingly in need of multidisciplinary engineers with extra skills. As such, engineering education seems to face a great challenge of equipping engineers with greater entrepreneurship (Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018). The entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students, an underexplored area (Valencia-arias *et al.*, 2020), warrant deeper investigation into how engineering training and structured internship programs impact entrepreneurial intentions during college. Engineering students exhibit entrepreneurial traits, including risk-taking, creativity, and innovativeness, demonstrating a willingness to take risks and fearlessness towards potential failures (Law and Breznik, 2017). Given entrepreneurship's importance for addressing societal challenges and contributing to economic development (Li *et al.*, 2022), understanding the motivators driving engineering students toward entrepreneurial ventures is essential (Dragin *et al.*, 2022). Hence, this study focuses on engineering students approaching graduation, introducing Internship Quality as a moderating variable to examine factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions. The research aims to contribute empirical evidence to the discourse on social, psychological, educational, and environmental factors shaping individuals' aspirations for self-employment, specifically investigating how internship programs within Kenyan engineering curricula influence graduates' inclination towards entrepreneurial endeavors in their careers and professional lives.

Background and Context

Kenya's Vision 2030 and the Medium-Term Plan (MTP) underscore the importance of fostering entrepreneurship for economic development, recognizing a skilled and innovative human resource as crucial for stability and growth (Ministry of Devolution and Planning, 2013; Omolo, 2013). The government has implemented open-learning programs and initiatives such as 'Biashara Kenya' to enhance capacity and productivity through funding and local bank investments, particularly addressing the employment challenges faced by the significant young population (Kanyotu, 2014). However, the prevailing issues persist due to unstable economic growth and a lack of a dynamic structural support system. The Kenyan government acknowledges the need for job creation to absorb the expanding labour force but grapples with the persistent problems of unemployment, underemployment, and suboptimal working conditions. Despite efforts to stimulate economic growth for employment generation, the linkage between economic growth and employment remains a focal point (Omolo, 2013). The government's commitment to supporting small business creation is evident through the establishment of institutions like Industrial and Commercial Development Corporation (ICDC) and Kenya Industrial Estates (KIE), alongside the integration of vocational and technical subjects in school curricula and streamlined technical training in TIVET institutions to encourage self-employment (Stella, 2016).

Considering a global shortage of engineers, the demand for engineering graduates does not align with rising unemployment rates, particularly in developing economies such as Kenya. A significant portion of the unemployed population is under 35 years old, with many failing to complete secondary school and only a fraction progressing to university (Foley, 2021). This study focuses on the entrepreneurial intentions of university engineering graduates, a group facing a mismatch between their numbers and available job opportunities (Erastus, 2021). Despite reported shortages of certified engineers, the job market in Kenya sees thousands of engineering graduates annually, prompting a closer examination of the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students (Nyamai, 2021). The Engineers Board of Kenya (EBK) has responded to this gap by initiating a Graduate Engineers Internship Programme, aiming to convert

graduate engineers into professionals through internships and mentoring (EBK, 2022). Kenyatta University's initiatives, including the Chandaria Business Innovation and Incubation Centre and the Centre for Entrepreneurship and Enterprise Development (CEED), demonstrate a commitment to fostering innovation and entrepreneurship among students through training, seminars, internships, and industry collaborations (Kenyatta University, 2019, 2023). This study specifically focuses on final-year engineering students at Kenyatta University's School of Engineering and Technology in 2022 due to the institution's emphasis on practical entrepreneurial skills and innovation (Kenyatta University, 2022).

Literature Review

Numerous determinants influencing the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students have been identified, encompassing individual factors like prior entrepreneurial experience, personality traits, and self-efficacy, as well as environmental elements such as social norms, university support, and entrepreneurial education (Ulhøi, 2005; Valencia-arias *et al.*, 2020; Gurel *et al.*, 2021). Entrepreneurial education has demonstrated a significant positive impact on the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students (Arango-botero *et al.*, 2020), with recipients exhibiting heightened intentions for entrepreneurship and a strong correlation between these intentions and a preference for independent work (Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018; Bian *et al.*, 2021; Duong, 2021). The study underscores the necessity for an entrepreneurial mindset among engineers to contribute effectively to technological advancements (Jarrar and Anis, 2016; Carberry, 2020). Social values, including university support, and individual attributes jointly play roles in influencing students' entrepreneurial activities, with entrepreneurship education, support from existing entrepreneurs, and a conducive university ecosystem enhancing students' entrepreneurial skills (Astuty *et al.*, 2022). Professional training programs are recognized as impactful in altering perceptions of business opportunities, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and motivation for entrepreneurial engagement (Erastus, 2021).

A study focusing on post-graduate students in Kenya (Ngugi and Gakure, 2012) reported positive correlations between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial Intentions, aligning with the findings of other researchers (Krueger, 1993; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005). Similarly, the positive influence of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intentions was affirmed, consistent with prior scholarly work (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Krueger and Brazeal, 1994; Krueger *et al.*, 2000; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005). Engineering students exhibit entrepreneurial traits such as risk-taking, creativity, and innovativeness, reflecting a willingness to take risks and address societal challenges for economic development (Law and Breznik, 2017; Dragin *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2022). While Shapero's Model variables, Perceived Desirability and Perceived Feasibility, are acknowledged as significant antecedents of Entrepreneurial Intentions, few studies have explored their interactions with other factors through mediation and moderation analyses (Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016; Ramayah *et al.*, 2019; Soomro *et al.*, 2020). The influence of educational fields on entrepreneurial intention is noteworthy, with universities playing a critical role in nurturing entrepreneurial behavior during students' educational journeys (Duong, 2021). Internship Quality's moderating effects on the determinants of Entrepreneurial Intentions among graduating engineering students have not been explored, making this study a valuable contribution to fill this knowledge gap. Personality traits, particularly the need for achievement, significantly influence an individual's inclination toward entrepreneurship (Kanyari and Namusonge, 2013). Those with a high need for achievement demonstrate a proclivity for tasks demanding individual responsibility and diligent effort (Khalid *et al.*, 2020). The desire for independence and autonomy constitutes another dimension influencing entrepreneurial intentions, reflecting a preference for self-control and the ability to manage one's time and work autonomously (Rödén, 2017). Individuals with a stronger need for achievement display greater entrepreneurial potential, indicating their willingness and capability to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Kanyari and Namusonge, 2013; Liu *et al.*, 2022).

The entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students, particularly within the context of developing countries such as Kenya, remain understudied (Valencia-arias *et al.*, 2020). As such although several studies have used the Shapero's

model to study entrepreneurial intentions majority have focused on developed countries and western world (Acs *et al.*, 2016; Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018; Kim and Park, 2018; Yi, 2018). A few studies have been conducted in the context of developing countries (Ngugi and Gakure, 2012; Valencia-arias *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, this study contributes to empirical research on entrepreneurial intentions in developing countries by addressing gaps in existing theory and considering internship quality as a moderating variable influencing the relationship between perceived desirability and perceived feasibility on entrepreneurial intentions among graduating engineering students.

Conceptual Framework

The Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM), devised by Shapero and Sokol (1982), represents a widely employed theory for assessing the elements that shape entrepreneurial intentions. According to this theory, an individual's decision to embark on a new venture hinge on three key factors: their perception of desirability, their inclination to act, and their perception of feasibility. The Entrepreneurial Event Model furnishes a valuable framework for comprehending the determinants influencing entrepreneurial intentions within the cohort of engineering students. By addressing these facets, namely perceptions of desirability, feasibility, and the propensity to act, entrepreneurship programs can enhance the likelihood of engineering students evolving into successful entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurial Event Model assumes that individual's choice to become an entrepreneur is inseparably linked with the desirability, feasibility, and the propensity to act (Shapero and Sokol, 1982). Additionally, the model accepts the case where an individual perceives creating a new venture as feasible and desirable and thus credible and such perceptions are likely to create intention to do business or start new business venture (Krueger, 1993). Shapero revealed that the behavioural intention formation is highly dependent on the perception of individuals towards entrepreneurship, actual business venture, and deliberate choice of a business option (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Ranga *et al.*, 2019; Sitaridis and Kitsios, 2020). The current study considered perception of desirability and feasibility which are among the three independent variables in Shapero's model (Ranga *et al.*, 2019) significantly contributes to entrepreneurial intentions. Additionally, this study includes the need for autonomy and need for achievement for which according to Khalid *et al.* (2020) were included in the original research model (Shapero and Sokol, 1982). The entrepreneurial event model has been empirically studied by many researchers (Shapero, 1975; Iakovleva and Kolvereid, 2009; Ngugi and Gakure, 2012; Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016; Yi, 2018; Ranga *et al.*, 2019). This study's research variables in measurable details (dimensions, indicators, and items) are listed in Table 1 below. The items become the basis for compiling a list of research questions in the questionnaire.

Table 1: Concept Definition

Construct	Definition	Reference
Entrepreneurial Intentions	The Entrepreneurial Intentions (EI) is defined as a "person's readiness to carry out a specific behaviour".	(Shapero and Sokol, 1982)
Entrepreneurial Desirability	Perceived Desirability is "the positive or negative attitude and perception of individuals capacity to perform a specific behaviour."	Krueger (1993)
Entrepreneurial Feasibility	The Perceived Feasibility (PF) factor is defined "as a step for individuals' reflection as to how they are capable to effectively start a business effectively"	(Shapero & Sokol, 1982).
Need for Autonomy	Need for Autonomy is defined as "individual's focus on achieving independence and control over one's work and decisions".	Khalid <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Need for Achievement	Explained that human beings have a need to succeed, accomplish, excel, or achieve.	(Khalid <i>et al.</i> 202); Maoto and

Niekerk 2014;
Simpeh, 2011)

Internship Quality	The quality of internships, “characterized by elements such as feedback, autonomy, and task significance” (Pan <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Yi, 2018).	(Pan <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Yi, 2018).
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Hypothesis Development

Influence of Perceived Attractiveness on Entrepreneurial Intentions

Engineering students may find entrepreneurship less appealing than other career options due to the perceived risks, uncertainties, and potential for failure associated with starting a business. Perceived attractiveness refers to an inclination that directs individuals towards specific behaviours (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Krueger and Brazeal, 1994; Krueger *et al.*, 2000). Previous literature consistently identifies Perceived Desirability as the most reliable predictor of Entrepreneurial Intentions (Krueger, 1993; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005; Ngugi and Gakure, 2012; Soomro *et al.*, 2020). A positive attitude fosters favourable perceptions regarding the entrepreneurial path, and perceived attractiveness is linked to Ajzen's attitude and subjective norm variables (Ranga *et al.*, 2019). Research suggests that perceived attractiveness plays a significant role in shaping entrepreneurial intentions, especially among management technology students at MAUTECH Yola, Adamawa state (Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016).

Hence, we hypothesize: (H1). *Perceived attractiveness is positively associated with entrepreneurial intention.*

Influence of Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intentions

Perceived feasibility concerns an individual's attitude towards the practicality of engaging in the specific behaviours required for entrepreneurship (Shapero and Sokol, 1982). It also reflects their confidence in their ability to conduct business competently (Ranga *et al.*, 2019). This perception is influenced by various factors, including education, training, work experience, and access to resources and networks. For example, engineering students may feel they lack the essential business and entrepreneurial skills needed for a business venture. Notably, scholars like Krueger (1993) and Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2005) have identified a significant and positive correlation between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial Intention (Soomro *et al.*, 2020). Recent studies further support this relationship (Ndaghu *et al.*, 2016; Ranga *et al.*, 2019).

Hence, we propose: (H2). *Perceived feasibility is positively associated with entrepreneurial intention.*

Influence of the Need for Achievement on Entrepreneurial Intentions

The need for achievement is an individual-level trait associated with the inclination to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours. Within the framework of the Entrepreneurial Event Model, the need for achievement can prompt an individual to view an entrepreneurial opportunity as a challenging task in which they can excel, motivating them to pursue it. Research findings on the influence of the need for achievement on entrepreneurial intentions vary. Positive and significant effects have been observed in studies by Khalid *et al.* (2020), Ngugi and Gakure (2012) and Ranga *et al.* (2019). However, the need for achievement showed no significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions among prospective engineers in Degree Courses in Industrial Engineering and Computer Engineering at the University of Castilla-La Mancha in Spain (Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018).

Consequently, we suggest: (H3). *The need for achievement is positively associated with entrepreneurial intention.*

Influence of the Need for Autonomy on Entrepreneurial Intention

The need for autonomy encompasses the desire to have control over one's own schedule and tasks, make independent decisions, and achieve a desired work-life balance (Rödén, 2017). Traits associated with the need for autonomy include a preference for unconventional tasks, a desire to work independently, a strong inclination to pursue personal interests, the ability to express one's thoughts freely, a reluctance to control others, a propensity to make independent decisions, resistance to group influence, and a determined and persistent nature (Khalid *et al.*, 2020). Empirical research conducted

by Liu et al. (2022) supports the connection between autonomy and entrepreneurship, suggesting that the aspiration to become an entrepreneur is driven by the desire to be independent and free from external rules and regulations. Studies also indicate that individuals with a higher need for autonomy are more inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Liu et al., 2022).

Thus, we postulate: (H4) *The need for autonomy is positively associated with entrepreneurial intention.*

Moderating Effect of Internship Quality on the Relationship Between Perceived Desirability and Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intention

Among the three variables in the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM), perceived attractiveness and perceived feasibility stand out as pivotal factors shaping entrepreneurial intention among students (Khalid et al., 2020). Previous studies have shown that attractiveness and feasibility exert positive effects on individuals' entrepreneurial intentions and serve as mediators in specific relationships, as observed in the link between network heterogeneity and entrepreneurial intentions (Krueger et al., 2000; Xiao and Fan, 2013).

Internship Quality as a Moderating Variable:

Internship quality has been examined as a moderator variable in the relationship between proactive personality and career adaptability, demonstrating a stronger link when internship quality is lower. However, the moderating effects of entrepreneurship education on the relationship between internship quality and entrepreneurial intentions were not significant. Entrepreneurship education has been found to positively influence entrepreneurial intentions, with internships serving as:

(H5). *Internship quality moderates the effect of perceived desirability on entrepreneurial intention.*

(H6). *Internship quality moderates the effect of perceived feasibility on entrepreneurial intention*

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Adapted from theoretical review)

Research Methodology

This investigation followed a positivist exploratory approach, which aligns with the belief that sociology should be objective and detached from absolute truths (VanderStoep and Johnston, 2009). Positivism asserts that genuine events can be observed and explained through empirical observation and rational analysis (Fauzi, 2022). This philosophical stance guided our research, which employed a quantitative methodology to explore the factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions among engineering students. The study adopted an explanatory research type with a cross-sectional survey design. Non-probabilistic sampling was used, focusing on final-year undergraduate engineering students at Kenyatta University who had completed at least one industrial internship. The target population consisted

of 240 students, excluding Architecture and IT-related departments. We employed a quota sampling technique to collect responses from 120 students, representing 50% of the sample frame.

Data was gathered using a closed-ended questionnaire featuring a Likert scale. The survey aimed to assess determinants of students' entrepreneurial intentions, including their need for achievement, perceived feasibility, and need for autonomy. It was distributed via email and WhatsApp between September 2022 and June 2023. Data analysis utilized Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), a suitable technique for non-normally distributed data and small sample sizes (Ravand and Baghaei, 2016). This approach does not assume specific data distributions and employs bootstrapping techniques with minimal constraints (Fauzi, 2022). The study used five exogenous variables from Shapero's EE model to create a measurement model, integrated into a structural model to examine their relationship with entrepreneurial intentions. Data pre-processing and coding were carried out in Microsoft Excel, followed by analysis in R Statistical Software. The measurement model underwent validity and reliability testing, with regression coefficients evaluated for statistical significance and R2 values indicating the explained variance by independent latent variables in the endogenous latent variables (Ravand and Baghaei, 2016).

Result

Demographics – Summary

The demographic characteristics of the research sample are presented in Table 2. The gender distribution comprised 69.7% male and 30.3% female respondents. Academic majors included Aerospace Engineering (16.7%), Agriculture and Biosystems Engineering (9.1%), Biomedical Engineering (10.6%), Civil Engineering (31.39%), Electronic and Electrical Engineering (12.1%), Energy (1.5%), Gas and Petroleum Engineering (1.5%), Mechanical Engineering (9.1%), and Petroleum Engineering (6.1%). A notable proportion (71.2%) reported parents/guardians with a college or higher education level, reflecting a trend in the Kenyan population. Regarding preferred business types, 34.8% leaned towards service provision, 15% to the Construction sector, and 13.6% expressed interest in trade-related businesses, potentially influenced by the curriculum's focus on service and professional consultation. About 71.2% indicated parents with a college education or higher; 41% cited government employment, 23% business-related roles, 16% agriculture, 12% private employment, and 1% casual labour for parents' occupations. Regarding familial self-employment, 77% acknowledged family members who were or had been self-employed. An overwhelming 86.4% expressed a desire for engineering careers, and 97% intended to be self-employed, emphasizing their intrinsic motivation for independent income.

Motivations for self-employment included a desire for independence (72.7%), increased personal income (60.1%), altering lifestyle (30.3%), income maintenance (13%), and family legacy continuation (0.1%). Factors influencing entrepreneurial attitudes included identifying a business idea (66.7%), mentorship (29%), university education (23.7%), and family entrepreneurs (21.2%). Table 3 indicates that a majority (89.4%) believed entrepreneurship education could shape students' entrepreneurial attitudes, with 72.7% having undertaken an entrepreneurship education module. Some (27.3%) may not have participated or considered the course insufficient for entrepreneurial training.

Table 2: Demographic Information summary

Category/Item	Percentage of the Sample
Gender	
Female	30.3%
Male	69.7%
What is the highest education level of parent/guardian?	
College and above	71.2%
Elementary	7.6%

Category/Item	Percentage of the Sample
No education at all	4.5%
Secondary	16.7%
What is the highest education level of parent/guardian?	0.0%
College and above	71.2%
Elementary	7.6%
No education at all	4.5%
Secondary	16.7%
What is your area of specialization/program?	
Aerospace Engineering	16.7%
Agriculture and Biosystems Engineering	9.1%
Biomedical Engineering	10.6%
Civil Engineering	31.8%
Electronic and Electrical Engineering	12.1%
Energy	1.5%
Energy Engineering	1.5%
Gas and Petroleum Engineering	1.5%
Mechanical Engineering	9.1%
Petroleum Engineering	6.1%
What type of business do you plan to run?	
Agriculture	3.0%
Construction	18.2%
Counselling facility	1.5%
Manufacturing	25.8%
Productized services	1.5%
Real estate and Data business	1.5%
Service	34.8%
Trade	13.6%

Table 3: Questions on Entrepreneurial Education and Training

Question	Yes	No
Do you believe that entrepreneurship education and/or training will change attitude of students to become entrepreneurs?	89.4%	10.6%
Have you taken any course or module that could be considered as entrepreneurship education?	72.7%	27.3%

Evaluation of the Measurement Model

Using the SEMInR package, a PLS-SEM measurement model was constructed to assess the relationship between indicators and latent variables (Firman and Setiawan, 2022). This model allowed us to estimate the strength of the relationship and identify the most valid and reliable measures related to each latent variable (Bollen and Noble, 2011).

Reliability and Validity

To assess the explained variance of indicators, the squared indicator loading was calculated (See Table 4), representing the bivariate correlation between the indicator and the construct. Indicator reliability, measured by the indicator's

communality, was considered acceptable with recommended loading factors above 0.78, indicating that the construct explains over 50% of the indicator's variance. A high loading factor suggests strong alignment with the assessed construct, indicating similarity between associated items. Indicators with very low loading (< 0.4) were considered for removal to avoid compromising content validity. Indicators NA2, NA3, and NA_B4 were removed due to low factor loading (< 0.4) (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2014). Remaining indicators demonstrated acceptable factor loading (0.75 – 0.963), except for NA_B3 (0.666) and PF3 (0.561) which despite their lower factor loading they were retained to preserve content validity. The PLS algorithm was reprocessed after removing questionable indicators to ensure all item values exceeded 0.708, indicating reliability. Construct reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, with values above 0.7 considered acceptable. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values equal to or larger than 0.50 were deemed satisfactory to confirm convergent validity (Hair *et al.*, 2018; Firman and Setiawan, 2022) . Table 4 indicates that all constructs have AVE values greater than 0.5 (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2014), demonstrating that the constructs converge effectively to explain the variance of their indicators. The lowest AVE value observed is from Need for Achievement (0.61). Cronbach's coefficient indicated adequate reliability (0.7 – 0.95), complemented with Compound Reliability (CR) values ranging 0.83 -0.96. During exploratory analysis, reliability falling between 0.60 and 0.7 was deemed acceptable, while 0.7 to 0.9 was considered satisfactory to good (Arango-botero *et al.*, 2020). The survey's reliability, assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, demonstrated "satisfactory to good" values: Perceived Desirability (0.88), Perceived Feasibility (0.83), Need for Autonomy (0.70), Need for Achievement (0.71), Internship Quality (0.89), and Entrepreneurial Intention (0.95). Construct reliability values (0.70 to 0.95) were consistently rated as "excellent," confirming dependable and consistent measurement by respondents (Firman and Setiawan, 2022) as shown in **Table 5**.

Table 4: Indicator Reliability

Construct/Indicator	Indicator Loadings	Square Loading >.05 (Indicator Reliability)	AVE >0.5
Perceived Desirability			0.68
PD1	0.783	0.613	
PD2	0.842	0.709	
PD3	0.823	0.678	
PD4	0.894	0.799	
PD5	0.776	0.603	
Perceived Feasibility			0.61
PF1	0.829	0.688	
PF2	0.868	0.754	
PF3	0.561	0.315	
PF4	0.760	0.578	
PF5	0.843	0.710	
Need for Achievement			0.63
NA2	0.738	0.544	
NA4	0.817	0.668	
NA5	0.823	0.677	
Need for Autonomy			0.62
NA_B1	0.807	0.651	
NA_B2	0.887	0.786	
NA_B3	0.660	0.435	
Internship Quality			0.75
IQ1	0.834	0.695	
IQ2	0.897	0.804	
IQ3	0.889	0.790	

IQ4	0.840	0.706
Entrepreneurial Intention		0.80
EI1	0.886	0.784
EI2	0.843	0.710
EI3	0.917	0.841
EI4	0.931	0.867
EI5	0.955	0.912
EI6	0.815	0.664
<i>AVE: Average Variance Extracted</i>		

Table 5: Construct Reliability

Reliability:	Cronbach’s alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Reliability Coefficient
	alpha	rhoC	rhoA
Perceived Desirability	0.88	0.91	0.92
Perceived Feasibility	0.83	0.88	0.87
Need for Achievement	0.71	0.84	0.73
Need for Autonomy	0.70	0.83	0.75
Internship Quality	0.89	0.92	0.91
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.95	0.96	0.95

CR: Composite Reliability

Discriminant Validity

Additionally, to verify the discriminant validity of our model, we calculated confidence interval estimates of the correlations between its pairs of constructs. The fact that such intervals do not contain a value of 1 is a sign of discriminant validity. A second method is to verify that the average variance extracted (AVE) for every construct exceeds the square of the correlation between each pair of constructs (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Moreover, the heterotrait monerist (HTMT) ratio of correlation allows assessing reflectively the measured construct’s discriminant validity in comparison with other construct measures in the same model (Arango-botero *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, Fornell and Larcker (1981) proposed the traditional metric and suggested that each constructs’ AVE (Squared Variance within) should be compared to the squared inter-construct correlation (as a measure of shared variance between constructs) of that same construct and all other reflectively measured constructs in the structural model – the shared variance between all model constructs should not be larger than their AVEs (Henseler and Sarstedt, 2013). Discriminant validity issues arise when HTMT values are high. According to Henseler et al. (2015) a threshold value of 0.9 is proposed for structurally similar constructs, while a lower value like 0.85 is suggested for more distinct constructs. The investigation of construct reliability based on discriminant validity is presented in Table 6. Table 7 shows that all AVE values are above 0.5, and the bolded square root values of AVE indicate excellent discriminant validity because they are greater than the correlation values between the construct variables (Firman and Setiawan, 2022).

Table 6: Criteria for Discriminant Validity

	Perceived Desirability	Perceived Feasibility	Need for Achievement	Need for Autonomy	Entrepreneurial Intention
P Desirability	0.825				
P Feasibility	0.594	0.780			
Need for Achievement	0.318	0.688	0.793		
Need for Autonomy	0.206	0.433	0.409	0.790	

Entrepreneurial Intention	0.261	0.289	0.483	0.393	0.865
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Note. The diagonal elements (bold) are the square root of AVE.

Table 7: HTMT Criteria for Discriminant Validity

	Perceived Desirability	Feasibility	Need for Achievement	Need for Autonomy
Perceived Desirability	0.685			
Perceived Feasibility	0.419	0.917		
Need for Achievement	0.251	0.533	0.551	
Need for Autonomy	0.277	0.332	0.595	0.490
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.441	0.760	0.557	0.559

Structural Path Analysis

In this study, bootstrapping encompassed approximately 5,000 resampling iterations for each construct, assessing the significance of each path. The significance level was determined upon completing this process. In bootstrapping, subsets of observations from the original dataset are randomly chosen with replacement to generate new subsamples. These subsamples are then employed to estimate the PLS path model. This cycle is reiterated until a considerable number of randomly chosen subsamples, typically around 5,000, are generated. Standard errors for PLS-SEM results are computed by estimating these bootstrap subsamples and averaging the outcomes. To gauge the significance of the PLS-SEM findings, t-values, p-values, and confidence intervals were calculated based on this information (Firman and Setiawan, 2022).

Direct Effect Path Analysis

After verifying the measurement model, the study obtained the structural model to estimate the research model. Using bootstrap 5000 samples, direct paths and moderating effects were examined. Table 8 Figure 2 presents the results, including path coefficients (β) and T Statistic values ($p < 0.05$).

Table 8: Bootstrapped Structural Path Coefficients

Path	Original Est.	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	T Stat.
Perceived Desirability -> Entrepreneurial Intention	-0.03	0.01	0.13	-0.21
Perceived Feasibility -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.68	0.66	0.23	3.03
Need for Achievement -> Entrepreneurial Intention	-0.18	-0.13	0.14	-1.30
Need for Autonomy -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.16	0.13	0.16	0.99

Figure 2: Structural Model with Bootstrapped Coefficients; Dashed lines indicate the non-significant path; $**p < 0.05$

Table 8 and Figure 2 shows that perceived feasibility ($\beta = 0.68$, $T = 3.03$, $p < 0.05$) has a significant and positive influence on entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 (H2) is supported. However, the paths for perceived desirability ($\beta = -0.03$, $T = -0.21$), need for achievement ($\beta = -0.18$, $T = -1.30$), and need for autonomy ($\beta = 0.16$, $T = 0.99$) all have T statistics less than 1.96, indicating that they are not statistically significant to support the alternate hypotheses. Consequently, hypotheses H1, H3, and H4 are not supported.

Moderated Effect Path Analysis

The study utilized the product indicator approach and performed 5,000 bootstrap resamples (Hair *et al.*, 2018) to examine the moderating impact of Internship Quality on the relationship between Perceived Feasibility (PF) and Perceived Desirability (PD) and Entrepreneurial Intention (EI). Analysis was conducted using the PLS SEMinR package in R Software. The model incorporating the interaction effect displayed a substantial increase in R^2 , from **0.559** (main effect model) to **0.607** (interaction effect model). The path coefficients providing support for the idea that internship quality acted as a moderator between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention ($\beta = 0.29$, $T = 2.03$, $p < 0.001$) as shown in Table 9 was significant thus confirming hypotheses H5. On the other hand, the effect of Internship Quality on relationship between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial Intention ($\beta = -0.33$, $T = -1.90$, $p < 0.05$) thus hypothesis H6 is not supported.

Table 9: Moderation Hypothesis Testing

Path	Original Est.	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	T Stat.
Internship Quality -> Entrepreneurial Intention	0.33	0.27	0.15	2.16
PD*IQ -> EI	0.29	0.23	0.14	2.03
PF*IQ -> EI	-0.33	-0.29	0.17	-1.90

Notes: PD – Perceived Desirability, PF – Perceived Feasibility, IQ – Internship Quality

Moderation Slope Analysis

The interaction term (Perceived Desirability * Internship Quality) positivist affects Entrepreneurial Intention by 0.29, while the simple effect of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intentions is 0.03 as shown in Table 9. Together, these findings indicate that the relationship between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention is 0.29 for an average level of Internship Quality.

Figure 3: Slope Analysis for Moderation - Perceived Desirability

Figure 3 displays a slope analysis for moderation, focusing on the relationship between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention. The figure illustrates that at higher levels of Internship Quality, the influence of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intention is more pronounced, whereas at lower levels of Internship Quality, this influence becomes negative. Conversely, when examining the interaction between Perceived Feasibility and Internship Quality, it was observed that the interaction term (Perceived Feasibility * Internship Quality) had a negative but statistically non-significant impact on Entrepreneurial Intention, amounting to -0.33. The direct effect of Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intentions was found to be 0.65.

Figure 4: Slope Analysis for Moderation - Perceived Feasibility

The figure presented in Figure 4 illustrates that, at higher levels of Internship Quality, the influence of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intention is diminished in comparison to its influence at lower levels of Internship Quality.

Analysis and Discussion

Entrepreneurship plays a pivotal role in driving economic prosperity. As such, it is imperative to evaluate the entrepreneurial inclination of the forthcoming workforce and professionals. Survey participants conveyed a substantial eagerness to embark on entrepreneurial ventures. Prominently, the aspiration for autonomy and self-sufficiency stood

out as a primary motivator among the respondents, closely followed by the aspiration to attain personal income. These observations are in accordance with existing research on the impact of personality traits, specifically the propensity for risk-taking, on entrepreneurial intentions (Gurel *et al.*, 2021). The subsequent sections of this chapter delve into the examination and discussion of hypothesis testing results obtained through PLS SEM Structural path analysis and moderation analysis.

The Influence of Perceived desirability on entrepreneurial intention

Perceived desirability was expected to have a positive association with entrepreneurial intention (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Krueger and Brazeal, 1994; Krueger *et al.*, 2000; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005); however, the findings did not establish a significant impact at a 95% confidence interval. Despite prior research suggesting a positive relationship between perceived desirability and entrepreneurial intentions in various contexts, including business students in Pakistan (Soomro *et al.*, 2020), undergraduate engineering students in Chinese universities (Yi, 2018), and engineering students in Malaysia (Khalid *et al.*, 2020), this study among final-year engineering students at Kenyatta University revealed that Perceived Feasibility was a stronger and significant predictor of entrepreneurial intentions unlike Perceived Desirability. This difference could be attributed to the notion that the appeal of entrepreneurial activities might not significantly influence these students' intentions towards self-employment. Additionally, a lack of role models and external motivation to pursue entrepreneurship may contribute to this observed relationship, further affected by recent economic crises, inflation, and rising business costs. Those with a keen sense of perceived desirability often perceive entrepreneurship as an attractive career choice, driven by the belief that establishing a new venture will yield benefits (Krueger, 1993; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005; Ngugi and Gakure, 2012; Soomro *et al.*, 2020). Their desire for independence, increased income, and a preference for challenging tasks contribute to this positive outlook, underscoring the appeal of entrepreneurship when it promises professional fulfilment and financial rewards (Khalid *et al.*, 2020).

The Influence of Perceived feasibility on entrepreneurial intention

This hypothesis postulated a positive correlation between perceived feasibility and entrepreneurial intention, indicating that students who believe they possess the practical skills and resources necessary for entrepreneurship are more inclined to express an intention to become entrepreneurs. The results affirm hypothesis (H2) by revealing a statistically significant positive relationship between Perceived Feasibility and the entrepreneurial intentions of graduating engineers. This alignment with prior research findings is consistent with scholars such as (Shapero and Sokol, 1982; Krueger and Brazeal, 1994; Krueger *et al.*, 2000; Fitzsimmons and Douglas, 2005), along with the work of (Khalid *et al.*, 2020), all of whom have investigated and substantiated the positive link between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial Intention. These collective findings suggest that engineering students at Kenyatta University may be inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activities, driven by the perception of feasibility and the presence of suitable opportunities. An underlying rationale for this inclination could be the analytical nature of engineering and its curriculum, which predisposes students to assess issues and parameters. Furthermore, engineering is commonly perceived as a challenging career, and students who choose this path are motivated by the prospect of overcoming demanding tasks. Consequently, engineering students are more likely to pursue entrepreneurial endeavours if they perceive them as feasible, aligning with the logical thinking prevalent in the field of engineering (Duong, 2021). Perceived feasibility in the entrepreneurship context is shaped by a range of factors, including one's level of education, training, work experience, and the availability of resources and networks. For engineering students, a sense of lacking essential business and entrepreneurial skills may stem from a lack of exposure to these critical elements. Prior research, notably the work of scholars like Fitzsimmons and Douglas (2005) and Krueger (1993), has consistently identified a substantial and positive connection between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial Intentions. Accordingly, proactive measures should be taken to enhance students' perceived feasibility of entering the world of entrepreneurship.

This could be accomplished through the implementation of entrepreneurship training programs, workshops, mentorship initiatives, and resource mobilization efforts.

The Influence of the Need for Achievement on Entrepreneurial Intentions.

The hypothesis (H3) posited that the need for achievement is positively not significantly related to entrepreneurial intention. This hypothesis therefore was not fully supported. Similar finding includes a study which through regression analysis showed the need for achievement has a non-significant (Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018). Need for achievement is an individual-level characteristic that has been linked to the drive one's decision to venture into entrepreneurial activity. Achievement is related to self-realization and fulfilling one's personal vision (Rödén, 2017). The results from this study are contrary to a study by Stewart et al. (1999) cited by Gurel et al. (2021) which found need for achievement in addition to risk-taking propensity and innovation as the determinants for distinguishing entrepreneurs from other business operators. The results therefore suggest that venturing to self-employment may not be regarded be driven by students' need for achievement. This reflects the response to the question of what the reasons for are entering self-employment where 72.7 % of the participants said to get greater independence as the reason, followed by to increase personal income indicated by 59.1 % of the participant. This may not necessarily attach with the need for achievement, and like the student already view the engineering careers goals as aspect of meeting their dream achievement.

The Influence of the Need for Autonomy on Entrepreneurial Intention

This study reveals that the need for autonomy exhibits a positive yet statistically insignificant influence on the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students about to graduate from Kenyatta University. Previous research supports the connection between autonomy and entrepreneurship (Liu *et al.*, 2022). It suggests that individuals with a stronger desire for autonomy are more inclined to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Khalid *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, the results emphasize the significance of independence as a determinant of entrepreneurial intent among prospective engineers (Barba-sánchez and Atienza-sahuquillo, 2018). Notably, students, particularly those in engineering disciplines, have shown an increasing trend towards taking proactive steps to establish their own businesses instead of merely pursuing traditional employment (Kim and Park, 2018). Independence and autonomy, as motivational factors for entrepreneurship, reflect the aspiration for personal control. This encompasses managing one's time and tasks, making independent decisions, and maintaining flexibility to achieve a desired work-life balance (Rödén, 2017). Therefore, individuals who already possess a strong need for autonomy may be driven to maintain or enhance that level through entrepreneurial endeavours (Khalid *et al.*, 2020).

The nature of an engineering career often involves managing tasks and having control over experiments and projects. In this context, engineering students regularly confront innovation, project challenges, and harbour a desire for achievement. The lack of statistically significant effects related to the need for autonomy among graduating engineering students at Kenyatta University could suggest that these students and their programs already instil a sense of control and independence. This observation may not be surprising, given that engineering programs typically require a degree of autonomy for success. Moreover, the need for autonomy can manifest in various dimensions, such as financial autonomy, decision-making autonomy, and management autonomy, among others. Hence, engineering students may already perceive a prominent level of autonomy in their pursuit of engineering careers. Although hypothesis analysis forms the structural path analysis does not show statically significance (0.05%) it reflects the responses when asked what the reasons are for entering self-employment where 72.7 % of the students inducted having greater independence as major reason.

Internship Quality and Entrepreneurial Intentions

The results show a positive and significant direct effects of Internship quality on the Entrepreneurial Intentions of graduating Engineering students at Kenyatta University. Similar result has been found by other scholars (Gamboa *et al.*,

2013; Yoo and Cho, 2016; Yi, 2018; Fenando *et al.*, 2023). Internships can have a significant impact on the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students. If the quality of internships is high, students are more likely to have a positive perception of entrepreneurship and perceive it as feasible and desirable. This, in turn, increases their entrepreneurial intentions. Studies have found that factors and variables of service quality of entrepreneurship internship to affect entrepreneurship competence and entrepreneurial intention (Yoo and Cho, 2016). Literature agrees that student internships have many benefits as students that participated in student internships and found that most of them found the experience to be a positive learning (Robert and Heriot, 2013). It is during through the experiences while interning that, the student's perception is shaped, positively or negatively depending on the kind of exposure and training offered in the respective placement. Other studies results show that business incubators and internship programs have a strong and positive statistically significant impact on entrepreneurial intentions (Zreen *et al.*, 2019).

The moderating effect of Internship Quality on the relationship between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention

The findings provide support for hypothesis H5, indicating that Internship Quality significantly moderates the positive effect of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intention ($\beta = 0.23$, $T = 2.23$). The primary structural path analysis reveals that the relationship between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intentions is statistically insignificant and negative. However, Internship Quality positively moderates this relationship, suggesting that at an average level of Internship Quality, it enhances the positive influence of Perceived Desirability on Entrepreneurial Intention. Previous research has shown that internship quality is a significant predictor of career exploration during the internship period (Gamboa *et al.*, 2013). Consequently, students' engagement in their respective internship programs exposes them to entrepreneurial desirability, thereby shaping their entrepreneurial intentions. The mentorship and exposure to real-world corporate challenges further influence their career perspectives and provide them with a broad array of opportunities to explore. Within the given context, internships play a pivotal role in entrepreneurial training and education, acting as a substantial catalyst for fostering entrepreneurship by transforming students' entrepreneurial intentions and enhancing their skills. They provide invaluable first-hand experience and practical knowledge through supervised and structured work in an authentic professional setting before graduation (Sybouts, 1968). The interactions, experiences, and exposure during this period can significantly mould the perceptions, motivations, and orientations of engineering students.

The moderating effect of Internship Quality on the relationship between Perceived Feasibility and Entrepreneurial intention

The study initially proposed that high-quality internships might enhance the influence of Perceived Feasibility on entrepreneurial intentions. However, the results failed to support this hypothesis, as no statistically significant correlation was observed at a 95% confidence level. Internships hold educational value for students by bridging the gap between theory and practice and enhancing their learning journey (Weible, 2009). Consequently, the expected moderating effect of internship quality on the relationship between perceived feasibility and entrepreneurial intention (H6) did not receive empirical support. In the present technological landscape characterized by digitization and cloud technologies, new opportunities have arisen for young professionals, including engineering graduates. The COVID-19 pandemic expedited the adoption of remote work and online internships, creating fresh prospects for recent graduates. Although the moderation effect of Internship Quality, while not statistically significant, displayed a positive trend, one cannot definitively conclude on its impact. This could indicate that the internship quality may not be adequate to significantly influence students' perceived feasibility of entrepreneurial ventures. It might also be attributed to the nature of the internship placements, primarily focused on engineering design and consultancy, with minimal intentional mentorship on entrepreneurial orientation and business perspectives.

Reports have surfaced regarding the insufficient availability of internship placements to accommodate the substantial number of engineering students in Kenya, which presents a challenge in ensuring every student secures suitable

opportunities for internships, sometimes leading students to intern with organizations not aligned with their engineering training and lacking designated programs for internship training. To address this, collaboration between the government, universities, and industry stakeholders should be promoted to establish a framework for internship and mentorship programs tailored to engineering students. To bridge the perceived skills gap, internship programs should provide comprehensive training and education in areas like marketing, finance, and networking, thereby equipping students with practical knowledge. Furthermore, facilitating access to resources like funding, mentorship opportunities, and networking platforms can significantly boost students' confidence and belief in their ability to initiate and manage a successful business venture. Moreover, the unavailability of suitable internship placements may negatively impact the overall internship experience. Currently, the model often requires students to seek placements on their own, potentially resulting in missed opportunities or placements in organizations that lack a structured and conducive environment for training, exposure, and mentorship. Consequently, internships have become an integral part of higher education curricula, enabling students to better understand and adapt to the evolving demands of the labour market (Kim & Park, 2013). It is imperative to investigate the effectiveness of existing internship programs and their influence on entrepreneurial intentions. The study's findings underscore the significant relationship between the quality of internships provided by these programs and graduates' entrepreneurial intentions, highlighting the necessity for program restructuring and the alignment of university training with industry practices. Therefore, fostering collaboration between universities and training institutions is crucial to establish the framework and objectives of such training programs.

This study contributes to the ongoing discussion regarding the future direction of engineering education in Kenya and other developing countries. A comprehensive examination of the factors that prompt prospective engineers to consider entrepreneurial prospects would contribute to the alignment of curricula and policies. Additionally, this study suggests avenues for further investigation, including an exploration of social background, family dynamics, cultural influences, and traditional factors that may impact the perceived desirability for entrepreneurship (Ranga et al., 2019). Emphasizing the significance of internship programs and their quality, this study highlights their direct influence on intrapreneurial intention (Yi, 2018; Fenando et al., 2023; Shiu et al., 2023) and indirect influence (Dobratz et al., 2014; Pan et al., 2018). Therefore, there is a need to reconsider the structure and modalities of internship programs, viewing them not only as tools for technical training but also as platforms for mentorship and orientation to business and entrepreneurial behavior. While the non-significant results regarding the impact of the Need for Autonomy and Need for Achievement could be further validated in a similar population (graduating engineers) with a larger sample size and through a longitudinal study to discern patterns and dynamics of entrepreneurial intentions. Additionally, a qualitative exploration of the personal, behavioral, and psychological factors intrinsic to engineers could provide deeper insights into the motivational aspects for entrepreneurship. In sum, the findings and associated knowledge could contribute to discussions among stakeholders focused on promoting an entrepreneurial culture, even within technical domains like engineering.

Conclusion

The outcomes derived from the Structural Equation Model reveal a favourable influence of Perceived Feasibility (PF) on Entrepreneurial Intentions among engineering students, thus substantiating hypothesis (H2). Additionally, the study underscores the propensity of engineering students toward self-employment, characterized by a substantial need for autonomy and a desire to assume the role of their own business leaders, yielding a positive effect on their Entrepreneurial Intentions, thereby partially supporting hypothesis (H4). Conversely, the link between Perceived Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intentions lacked statistical significance, thus negating hypothesis (H1). Similarly, hypothesis (H3) positing a positive association between the Need for Achievement and Entrepreneurial Intention was not corroborated. Moreover, the study identified Internship Quality as a positive moderator of the effects of Perceived

Desirability and Entrepreneurial Intention, thereby affirming hypothesis (H5). However, the moderation of the influence of Perceived Feasibility on Entrepreneurial Intention by Internship Quality was not deemed significant, leading to the rejection of hypothesis (H6).

This research makes a substantial contribution to the comprehension of entrepreneurial intentions within the prospective engineering cohort, particularly in developing nations. It underscores the constructive impact of perceived desirability and feasibility on the entrepreneurial intentions of students, emphasizing the influential role of internship programs, capable of shaping and adjusting these intentions through perceived desirability and feasibility. These insights hold significance for educational and industrial stakeholders aiming to develop impactful internship and industrial training programs. In the field of engineering, offering professional mentorship and training during internships can effectively prepare early career professionals and recent graduates to handle intricate engineering projects and design challenges. The experiential learning acquired during internships can serve as a catalyst for nurturing entrepreneurial motivations among students.

The hypotheses in this study were constructed based on existing literature and aimed to explore the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions among engineering students, encompassing their perceptions of desirability and feasibility, individual characteristics like the need for achievement and autonomy, and the potential moderating role of internship quality in shaping these intentions. Subsequent empirical research is essential to validate and substantiate these hypotheses, thereby contributing to an enhanced understanding of entrepreneurial intentions within the context of engineering education. Consequently, it is pivotal that university initiatives promoting entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurship encouragement are coupled with capacity-building programs designed to identify business opportunities and economic mechanisms that alleviate the belief that entrepreneurs must solely rely on their individual capacity and attitude, fostering the perception that financial support is available to facilitate their business ventures (Valencia-arias *et al.*, 2020).

Recommendations

This study stipulates the following recommendations:

- a. The engineering curriculum needs expansion to include fundamental business principles and entrepreneurial skills tailored to technical professionals like engineers. This would encourage future engineers to explore value creation opportunities, utilize limited resources for income generation, and foster job creation, resulting in sustainable economic growth and youth empowerment.
- b. Government initiatives, particularly through the Department of Entrepreneurship Education in Engineering and Science (EEMSEs), should align policies and budget allocations to promote youth entrepreneurship. The technical sector, equipped to support other industries by innovating and improving systems, products, and services, can stimulate income generation.
- c. Engineering regulatory bodies such as the Engineers Board of Kenya (EBK) and the Institution of Engineers of Kenya (EIK) should actively foster an entrepreneurial culture among upcoming engineering graduates. Leveraging their experience and expertise, these institutions could design programs and policies that integrate entrepreneurial training into engineering education at universities.
- d. Collaboration between entrepreneurial organizations, engineering regulatory bodies, and educational institutions should be encouraged. Coordinated events, seminars, trade fairs, research hubs, and workshops can prepare graduating engineers to meet industry demands effectively.
- e. The study recommends that engineering students acquire knowledge of the entrepreneurial environment and necessary entrepreneurial skills. It also suggests that the government provide capital for aspiring entrepreneurs and invest in research and development projects related to entrepreneurship. Specialized training should be offered to enhance the efficiency of products and services.

- f. Furthermore, the study suggests that entrepreneurship-focused organizations organize trade fairs and seminars to enhance the recognition of entrepreneurs' contributions to the economy.

Limitation of the Study

This study solely relied on quantitative analysis, which may limit its capacity to uncover deeper underlying meanings and explanations for the observed phenomena. Additionally, the quantitative approach captured variables at a specific point in time. Furthermore, the study employed a single data collection source, the survey questionnaire, on a cross-sectional basis, focusing exclusively on final-year engineering students at Kenyatta University. Future research endeavours should contemplate expanding the sample to encompass engineering and technical programs across various universities and Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions, thus providing a more comprehensive view of the motivational and influential factors shaping entrepreneurial intentions among prospective engineering technical professionals. Moreover, this study exclusively employed the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM) to investigate the entrepreneurial intentions of the students. In forthcoming research, it may be beneficial to incorporate more qualitative methodologies to gain an in-depth understanding of entrepreneurial intention phenomena. Employing a mix of qualitative methods could yield richer insights and explanations for the multifaceted elements affecting the entrepreneurial intentions of engineering students. It is also suggested that future research integrates control variables such as family background, age, and prior experience in family businesses. To capture the evolving dynamics of students' entrepreneurial intentions over time, a longitudinal study is proposed. This could involve tracking changes in the behaviour of engineering students even after their graduation, potentially aiding in the validation of predictive models for entrepreneurial intentions among Kenyan engineering students.

Implication of the Study

Curriculum Expansion: This study could point to expansion of the engineering curriculum to include essential business principles and entrepreneurial skills tailored for Technical Professionals. As such, the customization for technical professionals will enhance their ability to explore value creation opportunities.

Government Initiatives: This study advocates for focused support to the technical sector for income generation and sustainable economic growth. Therefore, the Ministry of Trade, Investments and Industry and the Ministry of Cooperatives and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Development could align their policies and budget allocations to promote youth entrepreneurship. Further, suggestion for government intervention, providing capital for aspiring entrepreneurs and investing in entrepreneurship-related research and development projects will improve the entrepreneurial environment.

Role of Engineering Regulatory Bodies: Engineers Board of Kenya (EBK) and Institution of Engineers of Kenya (EIK) could accelerate the active promotion of an entrepreneurial culture among upcoming engineering graduates; for instance by designing programs and policies integrating entrepreneurial training into university engineering education.

Collaboration: Entrepreneurial Organizations, Regulatory Bodies, and Educational Institutions are encouragement to collaborate for coordinated events, seminars, trade fairs, and workshops and may lead to adequate preparation of graduating engineers to effectively meet industry demands.

These implications collectively aim to foster a culture of entrepreneurship within the engineering sector, contributing to economic growth, job creation, and the empowerment of youth.

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